

SPREMEMBA VLADE IN NJEN VPLIV NA MEDIJSKO DEMOKRACIJO V MAKEDONIJI

Maja Blaževska-Evrosimoska <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9089-4601>¹

Žaneta Trajkoska <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9862-8637>²

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Povzetek:

Namen: Raziskati vpliv političnih sistemov na medije v kontekstu demokratizacije medijskega prostora. Osredotočiti se na izzive, s katerimi se soočajo mediji in novinarji v tranzicijskih družbah, ter na posledice teh izzivov za medijsko svobodo in širše družbeno okolje. *Metodologija:* Izvesti primerjalno analizo medijskih sistemov v različnih tranzicijskih družbah, s poudarkom na primeru Severne Makedonije. Uporabiti metodo kvalitativne analize vsebine, vključno z analizo medijskih poročil, novinarskih kod in intervjuji z novinarji in medijskimi delavci. Temeljiti analizo na relevantnih teorijah medijev, demokracije in tranzicije.

Ugotovitve: Politični sistemi močno vplivajo na medije, saj pogosto odražajo in reproducirajo obstoječe politične strukture in ideologije. Kratkoročne spremembe v izvršilni veji oblasti običajno ne vodijo k trajnostni demokratizaciji medijskega prostora. V tranzicijskih družbah se soočajo mediji in novinarji s številnimi izzivi, kot so politični vpliv, nadzor in kršitve novinarskih standardov. Politične stranke pogosto prevzemajo vlogo medijev, s čimer se izkrivlja vloga medijev kot neodvisnih nadzornikov družbenih in javno pomembnih procesov. Te težnje negativno vplivajo na medijsko svobodo, slabšajo položaj novinarjev in medijskih delavcev ter ovirajo demokratični proces.

Omejitve raziskave: Raziskava se osredotoča na omejeno število primerov in ne more generalizirati vseh ugotovitev na vse tranzicijske družbe. Vendar pa ponuja pomemben vpogled v izzive, s katerimi se soočajo mediji v teh družbah, in poudarja pome neodvisnih in svobodnih medijev za delovanje demokracije.

Praktične in/ali družbene implikacije: Ugotovitve raziskave so relevantne za oblikovalce politik, medijske delavce in civilno družbo v tranzicijskih družbah. Podpirajo prizadevanja za krepitev medijske svobode, neodvisnosti in profesionalizma, ter za spodbujanje pluralne in odprte medijske krajine.

Izvirnost: Raziskava ponuja nov in kritičen vpogled v kompleksne odnose med političnimi sistemi in mediji v tranzicijskih družbah. Prispeva k razumevanju izzivov demokratizacije medijskega prostora in poudarja pomen neodvisnih medijev za delovanje zdrave demokracije.

Ključne besede: mediji, politični sistem, demokracija, pluralizem, propaganda, manipulacija, nadzor.

THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT CHANGE ON MEDIA FREEDOM IN NORTH MACEDONIA

Abstract: The influence of political systems on the media is significant, as the media often reflect the political environment in which they operate. Changes in political structures affect both the media and society as a whole. However, short-term changes in the executive branch do not usually lead to the democratization of the media space. Examples of the transition from a communist system to a democracy, such as the case of North Macedonia, show the persistence of established patterns of behavior of political parties towards the media.

The journalistic profession often faces the inability to resist political influence and control, which is also reflected in violations of journalistic codes and standards. Political parties that use aggressive marketing and public relations strategies take on the role of the media, while the media and journalists become entangled in political conflicts. This leads to a distortion of their primary roles. These trends have a negative impact on media freedom, worsen the position of journalists and media workers, and make it more difficult for them to play their role as watchdogs of social and public processes. The consequences are also visible in the broader political environment.

Keywords: media, political system, democracy, pluralism, propaganda, manipulation, control.

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Korespondenčni avtor: Žaneta Trajkoska, zانات@iks.edu.mk

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¹ Al Jazeera Balkans, Filip Vtori Makedonski 3, Skopje, Makedonija; maja_blazevska@hotmail.com

² direktorica, Inštitut za komunikacijske študije, Yuri Gagarin 17-1/1, Skopje, Makedonija; zانات@iks.edu.mk

Introduction and literature review

The media outlets are the mirror of the society, inextricably linked to the overall societal and political context. The role of the media is to inform, educate and entertain, but they also carry the right of the public to be informed and involved in public interest processes. As one of the main correctors in society, their work is to point out the irregularities and publicly address the problems and open a debate on possible solutions. The first social value that affects the media outlets and the way of thinking about mass communication is freedom – it is the basis for opposing all paternalistic, authoritarian and manipulative uses of media outlets or the interference of the government or the church in the communication process. Freedom means open access to communication channels, resistance to manipulation and censorship and full freedom of expression with respect for others, including non-violation of the country security (McQuail, 1994). The most important comparative analyzes of media outlet systems show that they are shaped by a multidimensional set of areas and variables – from market mechanisms and economic forces to political area, the political system, and its features. Mass communication is considered a social, sociological, and cultural phenomenon, and the media outlets often take the shape of the political environment in which they operate. In order to perceive the differences in media outlet systems it is necessary to take a look at the social systems in which they work (Hallin and Mancini, 2004, 9).

Political and media outlet systems undoubtedly influence the processes, but they also influence each other. There are several theories that analyze the relationship between media and politics. According to the instrumentalization theory, the media is dependent on politics because it tries to direct the media and their political functions to its own benefit. (Kunczik and Zipfel, 2006). On the other hand, there are theories that the emergence of modern media has influenced politics. Such development is called "mediatization of politics", which means that the media outlets, especially television, have subordinated politics to their rules. When it comes to the mutual influence of the media outlets and politics, the media intrusion theory speaks of the fact that the media has taken the place and role of the politics (Baran and Davis, 2010). According to Hallin and Mancini, there are three models of media outlets and politics: the Mediterranean- polarized plural, the North European or democratic corporatist model and the North Atlantic or liberal model. However, due to the impossibility of including post-communist states, countries that do not belong to Western culture and new democracies in these models, they are defined as hybrid regimes (Vltmer, 2013).

North Macedonia, like the rest of the Western Balkans countries, is part of the hybrid regimes. Four decades ago, it began its transition to a democratic society, but it is still facing the post-communist legacy along the way. In addition to the changes in the political systems during the transition period, the democratization of the media outlets and the media legislation were difficult to implement. The public debates were based on the assumption that media legislation is unnecessary and that everything should be left to the free regulation of the ideologically and politically neutral market (Bašić and Petković and Jusić, 2004). It is impossible to eliminate the institutional traces inherited from the past when transforming the institutions that served the old regime, and those traces are not only present in the procedures and rules, but they also shape the expectations and behavior of the representatives of the institutions and external stakeholders (Vltmer, 2013, 12).

This paper will show that, in the short term, it is impossible to remove the features of the authoritarian rule despite the change of government and the process of democratization of the system, and that the matrices on which political representatives and the media outlets are used to work are difficult to change.

In order to examine the dilemma posed in the research question, in-depth interviews were conducted in 2017 and 2023 with ten most prominent representatives from the journalistic area in Macedonia: editors, journalists, professors of communication, leaders of media professional and professional organizations and journalistic associations, asking a set of questions related to the presence of political pluralism in the media outlets, the manner in which the media is instrumentalized, how political pressures have an impact on professionalism in journalism, journalistic autonomy and the economic status of journalists.

The Macedonian society underwent a long political crisis, which grew into the so-called 'Colorful Revolution' since 2016. Thousands of protesters took to the streets every day demanding justice after the then Macedonian president granted amnesty to 56 politicians and their associates, mainly suspects from the Special Prosecutor's Office for the wiretapped recordings published by the opposition. In those recordings, senior officials of the then ruling VMRO-DPMNE are involved in illegal activities – a party that has been in power for ten years by the time of the protests. During the period of rule of the right-wing VMRO-DPMNE, there was a sharp decline of 89 positions according to the Reporters Without Borders 'Media Freedom Index' – from 34th place in 2009 to 123rd place in 2014.

A change of government in 2017 brought a new government formed by the center-left party SDSM and the most popular party among the Albanians – DUI, which were also part of the previous Cabinet.

In order to determine whether, according to media outlet representatives, there has been a change in the democratization of the society and increase in media freedoms with the change of government that was previously led by a center-right party whose rule was defined as an "authoritarian regime", towards center-left parties or a democratic regime, a small experiment was carried out - the same questions were asked to the same editors and journalists both in 2017 and in 2023.

2017 – the captured media outlets in the captured state

The research conducted in 2017 concluded that the media outlets are not sufficiently strong to respond to political pressures and control, which is mostly of an institutional and economic nature. "The media show a low level of integrity because informational-promotional discourse with elements of propaganda dominated the news".³ The informing leans towards the political parties in power, and the media outlets are used in fighting against different opinions, but they are also involved in political conflicts, some created by themselves. "The practice of strong connection, in which the border between the government and the media is not present, was set by the government of the Prime Minister Nikola Gruevski, which spent 38 million euros from 2008 to 2015 on campaigns in electronic and print media. With this money, the Government directly influenced the editorial policy of the media and practically all the media had one editor, who sat in the government - it was the head of the Prime Minister's office".⁴ Due to political influences, the dissemination of fake news, even hate speech, is not a new phenomenon. "The captured state in Macedonia also captured the media outlets"⁵. In addition to political control, there is also the absence of a culture of debate, lack of diversity and pluralism in the media, including lack of political duels. "There was no space for the opposition in the public broadcasting service for years"⁶.

The analysis of the interviews shows that there is no real independence in the work of the media outlets, and the environment in which journalists work is unfavorable. The environment is also complemented by a feeling of lack-of-protection by judicial institutions. Topics of essential importance such as European integration, social issues, the rule of law, are absent in the media outlets. On the other hand, there is 'cheering' journalism and media framing according to party and government guidelines. The respondents point out the strong connection between the media owners and politicians. "Some of the media owners were directly involved in political processes as leaders of political parties"⁷.

Due to the influence of the ruling elites, the public broadcasting services cannot respond to the needs of the public interest. "The dominant power of the government over the media was mostly reflected in the public service"⁸.

The main conclusion of all the respondents is that the strengthening of the media, especially in terms of the economic aspect, is possible when the institutions are strengthened and the legislation and the self-regulation of the media outlets are improved, and when conditions for equal access to the advertising market will be created. These aspects are crucial for democratization of the media.

2023 - media environment in a familiar matrix

After six years, the same questions were asked to the same media professionals and editors who, for the most part, are still in the same positions in 2023, and those who are not leading the journalist associations in 2023 are working as chief media editors. All of them are active in the world of journalism, hold public positions and have a strong impact in the public sphere in Macedonia.

Analyzing their answers six years later, shows that there is no big change in the media landscape in terms of the media environment. Instead of political pluralism, political "bipartism"⁹ is present", and it is rare to hear the views of smaller political parties or opposing views from other representatives in the public. "There is strong hierarchism in the media"¹⁰, states one of the respondents. What is problematic, the respondents say, is the lack of criticism on the conveyed views of the political parties' or, in a worse case, obscuring of certain information from the public if they could have the potential to change the effect or the opinion of the public.

Political parties have assumed the role of media, by creating news and media content in the online and social media. The reaction of the media professionals is that those 'officers' cannot qualify as journalists. "You do not do transparency with aggressive PR, where part of the work of journalists is taken away, but a two-way communication and transparency is needed"¹¹.

In terms of the ethnic division in the media outlets, there are no different political pressures and influences in the Macedonian or Albanian language media outlets. "The media outlets did not perform the necessary function of integration"¹². Media owners remain the main link between political parties and media, and their influence on editorial policy is usually for lucrative reasons or personal interests. "The private televisions tell the government what advertisements it should make, how much, under what conditions they should be aired, how much they should cost, how they should be dispersed. Believe me, that did not exist even in the time of communism".¹³ It is concluded

³Interview with a professor of communication conducted on November 9, 2017

⁴Interview with a journalist in a television channel conducted on October 11, 2017

⁵Interview with the president of a journalist association conducted on November 12, 2017

⁶Interview with a journalist from a television channel conducted on October 11, 2017

⁷Interview with a professor of communication conducted on November 7, 2017

⁸Interview with a journalist from a news agency conducted on October 24, 2017

⁹Definition given by a media editor in an interview.

¹⁰Interview with a television editor conducted on June 30, 2023

¹¹Interview with a journalist in a television channel conducted on June 28, 2023

¹²Interview with a communication professor conducted on June 22, 2023

¹³Interview with a journalist in a television channel conducted on June 22, 2023

that the legal framework protects against political influences, but an impartial and non-selective implemented of those legal provisions is needed.

As for the public broadcasting service, there is less criticism in terms of politicization in contrast to 2017. Most of the respondents believe that this is the place where reforms in the media outlets should start. Reforming should also continue in the Agency for Audio and Audio-Visual and Media Services in order to influence other media to comply with standards and self-regulation. Journalists' associations are committed to improving the situation in the media space, but it is pointed out that greater engagement and influence on the owners, managers and chief editors in the media is needed.

Conclusion

When comparing the key insights from 2017 and 2023, several trends clearly show. The main one is that, despite some relaxation in the media, there is still no democratization in the true meaning of this notion. Indirect influences and copying the behavior of the authoritarian regime that ruled the country for more than a decade influence some respondents to feel "defeated when they believed that after the change of government, the media will serve the public interest." Political parallelism has sharply divided the country to the point where it is difficult to agree on any issue, or as Voltmer says, to accept the validity of an opposing opinion.

In order to have democratization of the environment in both the public space and in the media outlets, it is necessary to create equality in the advertising market and not to allow the re-introduction of the concept of public campaigns or government funding of private media. In such an environment, it is necessary to strengthen the influence of the public service and its credibility. However, most of the interlocutors say that a reduction in political influences is noticeable in the work of the public service for the last six years – there is no instrumentalization as it was the case in the previous research.

The democratization in the media outlets must be followed by a democratization of the rest of the areas and institutions in the country, that is to institutionally process the publicly known scandals and corruption cases in order to prove the impact of the media work. Although there is a difference in terms of economic status of journalists, in both surveys the economic situation of the journalists and low salaries are considered as one of the reasons for political influence on the media outlets. "A stable job and a solid salary are key for a journalist to remain immune to any control and influence"¹⁴.

In the context of media democratization, greater efforts are needed to strengthen the professionalization, especially at the faculties of journalism, which today barely enroll a dozen students. Priebe stated in his report¹⁵ that journalists do not have the skills to get information¹⁶, the political parties are generators of superficiality in the public space, the media must provide quality information, otherwise there will be an uninformed electorate in the country.

By analyzing the interviews and comparing the tendencies in the two periods, it can be concluded that there are certain indicators that show that the relaxation of politics or the democratization in the society as result of the change of government from authoritarian to democratic which lead to better media environment, but not to a great extent. The period of six years is not enough to see significant changes happening in media democratization and increased freedoms. This is also shown by the jump of 19 places in the ranking of Reporters Without Borders, who are stating that the spread of disinformation and low professionalism contribute to the reduction of public support for the media. Macedonia is placed 38th out of 180 countries on the media freedom index in 2023. That is the best position since 2009, however, we must note the changed methodology used to prepare this index.

Six years since the change of the government and democratization of the country, according to Freedom House, Macedonia is still a partially free country. In its report, they describe the media space in the country as deeply polarized along political lines, and the private media connected to political and business interests.

The determination of the political parties in creating media content and their work as media outlet 24/7 is also a factor that does not contribute towards changing the situation. In addition, the reluctance of the media to adapt to new technologies, usage of social media and media transformation is also a factor in the weak democratization of the media and their complete freeing of the party influence. The media are a mirror of the society, inextricably linked to the entire societal and political context, thus the state of democracy in the country is not at a desirable level. Media and political systems affect the main processes in the countries, but above all they also affect each other. Professionalization and compliance with higher ethical standards in both areas is the key towards strengthening the public awareness and its right to be informed. Without improvement of the media environment, there will be no improvement of the democratic capacities of the society as these relations are interdependent, depending on each other in the negative context of pressures and influences as well.

¹⁴Interview with an editor in the public service conducted on June 29, 2023.

¹⁵The report is cited in the references.

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